

The Study of Bacteriology and Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern of Tubo – Tympanic Type of Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media at Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Aim: To study the antibiotic susceptibility pattern of the bacteria isolated in Tubo-tympanic (TT) type of Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM).

Materials and Methods: Based on predetermined inclusion-exclusion criteria, 189 patients were enrolled in the study. Ear discharge samples were collected and subjected to aerobic bacterial culture procedure. Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method was used for assessing antibiotic susceptibility.

Results: Staphylococcus aureus was the most prevalent isolate (32.78%) followed closely by Pseudomonas aeruginosa (25.00%). The Antibiotic Susceptibility Profile of S. aureus revealed Linezolid, Teicoplanin and Ampicillin-Sulbactam as the most effective options, with sensitivities of 98.31%, 94.92%, and 94.92% respectively. Levofloxacin and Ciprofloxacin exhibited the highest resistance levels at 81.36% and 79.66% respectively. For P. aeruginosa, Doripenem and Meropenem emerged as the most effective options, displaying sensitivities of 91.11% and 86.67% respectively. Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin exhibited resistance to these drugs, with values of 20.00% and 28.89% respectively.

Conclusion: Because of the high prevalence of fluoroquinolone, penicillin, and macrolide-resistant S. aureus we should cautiously use these groups of antibiotics in patients of CSOM. To reduce the occurrence of resistant strains and encourage the efficient use of antibiotics, culture is recommended in all actively discharging cases of a TT Type of CSOM.

Keywords: CSOM, Aerobic Culture, Resistance, Sensitive, Antibiotic Susceptibility.

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Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines Chronic suppurative Otitis Media (CSOM) as a middle ear cleft inflammation that is chronic and discharges frequently for at least three months [1,2]. In developing countries, it is a major cause of acquired hearing impairment. Due to Hearing loss, language and cognitive development in children is affected. [3,4]

Streptococcus pneumoniae, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, and *Haemophilus influenza* are the most common causative organisms causing CSOM^[2]. Climatic conditions, local practices and geographical distribution plays an important role in the types and antibiotic susceptibility patterns of organism involved in CSOM. [5, 6].

Low socioeconomic status, substandard living conditions, inadequate cleanliness, malnutrition, overcrowding, insufficient antibiotic treatment, inap-

propriate drug selection, and antibiotic misuse are major contributing factors to the occurrence of CSOM in underdeveloped countries [7]. A higher prevalence rate of CSOM is seen in poorer rural communities as compared to urban communities [8]. According to WHO research, the prevalence of CSOM in India is 7.8%, placing it, in the highest category.

The in-vitro antibiotic susceptibility pattern is crucial for clinicians to begin an appropriate treatment plan for CSOM. Not all the patients in our country can afford the cost of the laboratory tests. Thus, some empirical options need to be laid out for such patients. To complicate the issues further the over-the-counter drug availability is a very common practice in developing countries. The rampant use of antibiotics in the COVID period could have affected the bacteriological pattern and antibiogram CSOM patients. This study was carried out to rec-

ognize the shifting composition of the bacterial flora and their susceptibility patterns in the CSOM.

Materials and Methods

This observational study was conducted following approval from the institutional ethics committee. The study enrolled 189 patients aged 14 years or older, who were presented with ear discharge lasting for at least 6 weeks and evidence of tympanic membrane perforation. These patients had not received any form of antibiotic therapy (topical or systemic) for the past 2 weeks. Patients with Inactive disease, cholesteatoma, otitis externa benign and malignant neoplasms, with history of past ear surgery – tympanoplasty or mastoidectomy, were excluded from the study. All the patients provided informed written consent prior to enrollment. Detailed clinical information including age, gender, duration of discharge, and relevant medical history was documented for each participant as per the proforma.

Sample Collection and Processing

Demographic data, clinical history and examination of the patients was done as per the proforma. The samples were taken from the middle ear in case of large perforations and from the surface of small perforations under aseptic conditions. Gram Staining, Culture on Mac Conkey agar, chocolate agar and blood agar was used for swab processing. Kirby Bauer Disc Diffusion Method on Mueller-Hinton agar plate was used for Antimicrobial Susceptibility according to CLSI guidelines [9] for all Aerobic Isolates.

Results

In this study, a total of 189 patients were included, with the majority falling within the first and second decades of life. Specifically, there were 63 patients aged 14–20 years and 62 patients aged 21–30 years. The average age of all patients was 34.28 ± 10.58 years. The gender distribution showed a ratio of 1 male to 1.7 females, with 118 females (62.43%) and 71 males (37.57%). Among these patients, the largest group comprised of homemakers, accounting for 86 individuals (45.50%). School or college students constituted the second most common group with 32 patients (16.93%), while businessmen were the least represented, with only 19 patients (10.05%).

Regarding the socio-economic status of patients, most of them belong to the lower middle class (94, 49.74%) as per the modified Kuppuswamy-scale [10] with the least number in the lower class (12, 6.35%). The patients were largely from rural areas (132, 69.84%) and only 57 (30.16%) belonged to the urban areas. Unilateral CSOM was seen in 146(77.25%) patients and 43(22.75%) patients had bilateral CSOM. In twelve patients with bilateral CSOM the second ear did not fulfill the inclusion criteria. Therefore, for the simplicity of analysis only one ear sample was taken from the patients

with bilateral ears CSOM.

Ear discharge was leading symptom. Mucoïd discharge was seen in 84 (44.45%) patients, copious in 121 (64.02%), and non-foul smelling in 131 (69%) patients. A lot of patients 69(36.51%) had upper respiratory tract infection at the time of presentation. The mean duration of ear discharge was 5.89 ± 2.68 years. Hearing loss was observed as the second most common symptom (111,58.73%). Hearing loss was observed as the second most common symptom 111(58.73%). Most patients had conductive hearing loss 102 (53.96%). 37 (19.57%) had mixed hearing loss and only 2 cases had Sensorineural hearing loss. It is noteworthy that 48 patients had no hearing impairment (less than 25db). A mild degree of hearing loss was seen in 76(40.21%) cases. Moderate sized perforation was seen in 88 cases (46.56%). Small perforations were slightly less frequent, accounting for 69 cases (36.51%), while large perforations were observed in the smallest proportion, with 32 cases (16.93%). Otagia was the next frequent complaint reported (75, 39.68%). Headache, Vertigo and Tinnitus were seen in 34 (17.99%),20 (10.58%) and 14 (7.41%) cases respectively.

After bacterial culture no growth was seen in 41 (21.69%) cases. The most prevalent isolate was *Staphylococcus aureus* (59,32.78%) followed by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (45,25%) and *Coagulase-negative Staphylococcus* (21, 11.67%). Other isolates such as *Klebsiella*, *Proteus sp.*, *Citrobacter*, *Escherichia coli*, *Providencia*, and *Acinetobacter* were less common, in that order. Polymicrobial growth pattern was observed in 9 cases (5.00%). Among this most common combination was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus aureus* with *Klebsiella* (2 cases each).

Linezolid, Teicoplanin, and Ampicillin-Sulbactam were found to be the most effective options for *Staphylococcus aureus* with sensitivities of 98.31%, 94.92%, and 94.92% respectively. On the other end of the spectrum, Levofloxacin, Ciprofloxacin and penicillin showed the highest resistance levels, with 81.36%, 79.66% and 50.85% respectively. Penicillin, Cefoxitin, Erythromycin, and Tetracycline also displayed significant levels of resistance.

Doripenem, Meropenem, and Piperacillin-Tazobactam emerged as the most effective options for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, displaying sensitivities of 91.11%, 86.67%, and 84.44% respectively. Coagulase-negative *Staphylococcus* isolates displayed high sensitivity to Gentamicin (95.24%) and Doxycycline (95.24%). Levofloxacin and Ciprofloxacin both demonstrated high resistance levels at 66.67%.

Meropenem, Doripenem, and Imipenem demon-

strated the highest sensitivity pattern, with all three antibiotics showing 83.33% effectiveness against the *Klebsiella* strains. Ampicillin-Sulbactam, Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin, exhibited the highest resistance levels, all with 50.00%.

The *Citrobacter* strain and *Escherichia coli* strain exhibited high sensitivity to most of the antibiotics tested. No resistance was observed for them for any of the antibiotics tested.

Discussion

The present study was undertaken on 189 clinically diagnosed tubo-tympanic types of CSOM patients. Out of 189 cases, most patients belonged to the second decade of life (14-20 years) making up 33.33% of the total cases. This is in concordance with the finding of various other studies [11,12] while Das C et al. [13] reported higher incidences in the third decade of life. We found a higher female predominance, which is to similar study done by Wan Draman WN et al [14]. In contrast, studies done by Kombade S et al [15], Geeta G et al [16], and Hiremath B et al [12] reported a male predominance.

Socio-economically the lower middle-class category (49.74%) was most common, these findings correlated with other similar studies. [12,17,18]. In accordance with our study, a high rate of unilateral involvement was also recorded by Wan Draman W et al [14], Das C et al [13], Kumar R et al [19], and Geeta G et al [16].

In the present study, ear discharge was the symptom reported by all the patients as seen in other studies [13,14]. In our study, mucoid discharge predominated (44.55%), contrasting with Wan Draman W et al [14].'s finding of mucopurulent discharge (48.4%) as most common, yet non-foul-smelling discharges correlated with upper respiratory tract infections, consistent with their research. In present patients presented with conductive hearing loss 64.86 % (72 patients) which is in concordance with another similar study by Mahdiani et al [20] (67.2%)

In the present study, 78.31% (148) of cases were culture positive which is like other studies by Ritu Gupta et al [21] and Kumar R et al [19] while in contrast Singh AH et al [22] showed 94.67 % of culture-positive cases.

Similar to present study *Staphylococcus* (32.78%) was the most common bacterial isolate seen by Das C et al [13] (35.86%), but Wan Draman et al [14] (32.6%) and Kombade S et al [15] (55.8%) found *Pseudomonas* to be the most common isolate. However, Rangaiah ST et al [23] found almost equal isolates of *Staphylococcus* (31.8%) and *Pseudomonas* (31.1%).

Above mentioned studies show that depending on

the population of patients and different geographical area the bacteriological profile varies and because of this, we need continual analysis and updates of bacteriological flora in every zone.

Staphylococcus aureus was shown to be extremely sensitive to ampicillin-sulbactam, teicoplanin, and linezolid in our investigation; their respective sensitivities were 98.31%, 94.92%, and 94.92%. Because of resistance to Penicillins, Macrolides, and Fluoroquinolones these must be utilized with caution. Similarly, Hiremath B et al [12] found that *S. aureus* was highly sensitive to Erythromycin (71.05), Ampicillin (55.26), and Linezolid (100%), conversely, the highest resistance was seen against Ciprofloxacin (78.9%) followed by Amoxicillin-clavulanate (55.26%).

In the current study, maximal sensitivity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was seen for Doripenem (91.11%), Meropenem (86.67%), Piperacillin-Tazobactam (84.44%), and Imipenem (84.44%). Fluoroquinolones were found to be resistant so they should be used with caution. Similarly, Das C et al [13] and Wan Draman W et al [14] observed that maximum sensitivity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was seen for Polymyxin B, Meropenem, Cefoperazone, Piperacillin-Tazobactam, Ceftazidime. Moreover, Mansoor T et al [24] report increased resistance rates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* towards Fluoroquinolones and Carbapenems.

In our study, Coagulase-negative *Staphylococcus* isolates had maximum sensitivity to Gentamicin (95.24%) and Doxycycline (95.24%), but Fluoroquinolones were found to be resistant so they should also be used with caution. Similarly, Geeta G et al [16] observed that Coagulase-negative *Staphylococcus aureus* was sensitive to Gentamicin, Doxycycline, Vancomycin, Linezolid, Chloramphenicol, and Amikacin. In contrast to our study, Das C et al [13] observed high sensitivity of Coagulase-negative *Staphylococcus* to Ciprofloxacin followed by Linezolid and Vancomycin.

In the present study concerning *Klebsiella* strains Ampicillin-sulbactam, Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin showed the highest resistance levels, all displaying 50.00% resistance. Additionally, Tobramycin and Piperacillin-Tazobactam both showed 66.67% resistance. In comparison to our study, the high sensitivity of *Klebsiella* to Polymyxin B followed by Meropenem, Cefoperazone plus sulbactam and Ciprofloxacin was seen by Das C et al [13].

In the current study, Gentamicin, Piperacillin-Tazobactam, Ciprofloxacin, and Levofloxacin showed 100.00% sensitivity to *Proteus* sp. Strains. In contrast to our study, Kombade S et al [15] et al, Wan Draman W et al [14], and Geeta G et al [16] observed 100% sensitivity of Amikacin, Ceftriaxone, Cefuroxime, Ceftazidime, Cefotaxime,

Imipenem, Piperacillin-Tazobactam, Cefepime, and Gentamicin.

In our study, the *Citrobacter* strain had 100.00% sensitivity to Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin, Gentamicin, Amikacin, Tobramycin, Teicoplanin, Piperacillin-Tazobactam, Ampicillin-Sulbactam, Ceftriaxone. In contrast to our study, Das C et al [13], observed sensitivity of Meropenem (91%), Ciprofloxacin (79%), and Cefoperazone Plus Sulbactam (90%). Kombade S et al [15], Hiremath B et al [12], and Harshika Y et al [25] reported high sensitivity of *Escherichia coli* to Polymyxin B (100%).

In the current study, the *Escherichia coli* strain displayed 100% sensitivity to Levofloxacin, Gentamicin, Amikacin, Ampicillin-Sulbactam, Piperacillin-Tazobactam, Ceftriaxone. Notably, no instances of resistance were observed for any of the antibiotics tested, similar results were obtained by Das C et al [13], Wan Draman W et al [14] and Geeta G et al [16].

Conclusion

Due to the increasing trend of bacterial resistance, it is now recommended to evaluate the susceptibility pattern of bacteria against the commonly used antibiotics for tubo-tympanic types of CSOM. Given the high prevalence of fluoroquinolone, penicillin, and macrolide resistance among *Staphylococcus* strains in this region, we strongly recommend conducting bacteriological profiling for patients with chronic suppurative otitis media whenever feasible. To reduce the resistance of antimicrobials to commonly used antibiotics for the tubo-tympanic type of CSOM, all actively discharging patients should be considered for routine pus culture and sensitivity testing.

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